

Fatigue tests on tubular joints with different load ratios to quantify the mean stress effect

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ABSTRACT

In the verification of fatigue-loaded tubular structures the welded connection becomes mostly decisive due to the low fatigue strength of tubular joints. High residual stresses are generated in the component as a result of the welding process. If no stress-relief heat treatment has been carried out, the mean stress effect is not to be considered in the IIW-guideline or EN 1993-1-9. Preliminary fatigue tests on X-joints made of high-strength austenitic steel that were not subjected to thermal stress relief showed a significant mean stress effect that is underestimated by said standards. Further tests on rail clamps subjected to compressive stress ranges showed a highly increased fatigue strength compared the normative detail category. To develop a solid database to safely and economically consider the mean stress effect in fatigue loaded tubular connections that were not subjected to thermal stress relief, the research project FOSTA P1603 is carried out by the University of Applied Sciences Munich. Therefore, fatigue tests on X-joints with up to 4 different load ratios are carried out. The test results will be then numerically interpreted to develop a design recommendation for the nominal and notch stress concept. In this paper the test series, the test setup and previous results of fatigue tests will be presented.

Keywords: hollow section, mean stress, tubular joint

1 INTRODUCTION

Steel hollow sections are often used in fatigue-loaded structures like commercial vehicles, cranes, barriers or bridges, see Fig. 1. In the verification of the structure the welded connection becomes mostly decisive due to the low fatigue strength of welded tubular joints. Thus, the potential of high-strength steels cannot be exploited leading to uneconomical designs.

High tensile or compressive residual stresses are generated in the component because of the welding process from solidification. The mean stress effect is not to be considered in codes of practice like the IIW-recommendations (1) or EN 1993-1-9 (2) to be on the safe side, unless the components were subjected to thermal stress relief. Preliminary fatigue tests (3) on X-joints made of high-strength austenitic steel that were not subjected to thermal stress relief showed a significant effect of mean stress that is even underestimated by the recommendation for components with low residual stresses acc. (1). Further tests on rail clamps subjected to compressive stress ranges showed a highly increased fatigue strength compared to the normative detail category (4).

a)

b)

c)

d)

Fig. 1. Examples of fatigue-loaded tubular structures – a) Commercial vehicles, b) Cranes, c) Barriers, d) Bridges

To develop a solid database to safely and economically consider the mean stress effect in fatigue-loaded tubular joints that were not subjected to thermal stress relief, the research project FOSTA P1603 (5) is carried out by the University of Applied Sciences Munich. Therefore, fatigue tests on X-joints with up to 4 different load ratios, plate thicknesses, steel grades, loading types and sections shapes are investigated in 9 different test series. The test results will then be numerically interpreted to develop a design recommendation for the nominal and notch stress concept. In this paper the test series, the test setup and previous results of fatigue tests will be presented.

2 STATE OF THE ART

2.1 Normative Situation

Welded joints of hollow sections that were not subjected to thermal stress relief have medium or high residual tensile stresses. In this case the design standards EN 1993-1-9 (2) or ISO 14347 (6), the IIW-Recommendations (1) or the CIDECT-8 guideline (7) do not consider a mean stress effect at all or only a small amount. If the residual stresses of the component would be relieved, (1) and (2) allow an reduction of the compressive part of the stress range by 40%, see Fig. 2. According to (1) the fatigue resistance can alternatively be enhanced by the factor $f(R) = 1.6$ for load ratios R lower than -1 , or $f(R) = -0.4 * R + 1.2$ for load ratios R between -1 and 0.5 .

Fig. 2. Left) Reduction of the compressive part of the stress range acc. (2), right) enhancement factor acc. (1)

2.2 Existing research on fatigue-loaded welded tubular joints with different load ratios

The database for fatigue tests on tubular joints with different load ratios is limited. Most tests found in literature were performed with a load ratio $R = 0.1 - 0.2$. For this section, the data of the few existing tests that were performed with different load ratios was analysed in excerpts. The fatigue strength of the tests was evaluated at 2×10^6 load cycles with a fixed slope of $m = 5$ and a survival probability of $P = 50\%$. In (8), 3-point bending tests on T-joints made of cold formed thin-walled circular hollow sections (CHS) ($t = 1.17$ mm, unknown steel grade) were performed with 4 different load ratios. In (9), fatigue tests on K-joints made of CHS (chord: 177.8×8.0 , brace 88.9×4.5 , steel grade: S235) with axial brace loads were performed with 2 different load ratios, see Fig. 3. The results show a slightly higher fatigue strength for the load ratio $R = -1$ in comparison to the load ratios with fully tensile stress ranges. However, due to the large scatter of the test results no reliable mean stress effect can be detected. It should also be noted that the sample size of $R = 0$ ($n = 4$) is much smaller than that of $R = -1$ ($n = 24$). Fatigue tests with fully compressive stress ranges were not found. Thus, the existing database is not sufficient to quantify a mean stress effect for fatigue-loaded tubular joints.

Fig. 3. Test results of existing research projects – a) Tests on CHS-T-joints (8), b) Tests on CHS-K-joints (9)

3 RESEARCH PROJECT P 1603

As shown in 2.1 and 2.2 the design standards and literature do not suggest a clear mean stress effect for fatigue-loaded tubular joints. However, preliminary tests performed at the Laboratory for Steel and Light Metal Construction of the University of Applied Sciences Munich (3) showed a not negligible mean stress effect for X-joints made of cold formed thin-walled square hollow sections (SHS) (chord/brace: 50×2.0 , steel grade: 1.4678) under bending loads, see Fig. 6. Therefore, the research project FOSTA P 1603 (5) was applied for to create a solid database to safely and economically consider the mean stress effect in fatigue loaded tubular connections that were not subjected to thermal stress relief.

3.1 Test series

To systemically quantify the mean stress effect on tubular joints 146 fatigue tests in 9 different test series with up to 4 different load ratios are performed, see Table 1. To expand the data base the test matrix will be complemented by test results of identical specimens from (3, 10). All X-joints were made with circumferential fillet welds (MAG process).

Table 1. Overview – test series

series	load type	chord	brace	β [-]	γ [-]	τ [-]	steel grade	load ratio	number of specimens
A	IPB						S460MH	-1	12
								0.1	4 + 11 (10)
								0.5	12
B		SHS 50x2.0	SHS 50x2.0	1.0	12.5	1.0	1.4678	-1	12
								0.1	12 (3)
C	AX						S460MH	„-∞“	8
								0.1	8
D							1.4678	-∞	8
								0.1	8
E	AX	SHS 100x4.0	SHS 50x4.0	0.5	12.5	1.0	S355J2H	„-∞“	7
								-1	7
								0.1	2 + 10 (10)
F							S700MH	0.5	7
								-1	7
G	AX	SHS 200x8.0	SHS 100x8.0	0.5	12.5	1.0	S355J2H	-1	3
								0.1	3 (10)
H	AX	CHS 101.5x5.6	CHS 51x4.0	0.5	18.1	0.71	S355J2H	0.5	4
								„-∞“	4
								-1	3 + 7 (10)
I	IPB	RHS 300x100x10	RHS 400x400x20	0.25	10	0.5	S620QLH	0.5	3
								„-∞“	3

IPB = in-plane bending, AX = axial forces

3.1.1 Load types and ratios

The investigated load ratios range from fully tensile stress ranges ($R = 0.5$, $R = 0.1$) to alternating ($R = -1$) and fully compressive stress ranges ($R = \text{“-∞”}$), see Fig. 4. The different load ratios are applied as in-plane bending moments (IBP) and axial forces (AX).

Fig. 4. Investigated load ratios

3.1.2 Steel grades

To quantify the influence of the material, 5 different steel grades i.e. mild steel S355J2H and fine grain steel S460MH acc. EN 10219-1 (11), fine grain steel S700MH acc. EN 10219-3 (12), quenched and tempered steel S620QLH acc. EN 10210-3 (13) and austenitic stainless steel 1.4678 acc. prEN 10088-2 (14) will be tested.

3.2 Test setup

For the AX-tests 2 high-frequency resonance pulsators (600 kN and 50 kN maximum amplitude) and a hydraulic cylinder (40 kN) are used depending on the maximum/minimum load and the specimen size. The specimens subjected to small amplitudes (< 20 kN) are clamped mechanically, in case of large amplitudes the specimens are welded to a connection plate which is clamped hydraulically. The IBP-tests are also performed in pulsators but the load is applied via a traverse, see Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Test setups – AX-tests: a) pulsator (50 kN amplitude), b) pulsator (600 kN amplitude), c) hydraulic cylinder (40 kN) IPB-tests: d) pulsator with traverse for load application

The clamping stresses are measured via strain gauges that are applied to the walls of the braces parallel to the clamping wedges. To determine the shift of the mean stress due to the clamping stresses the strain gauges are pre-cycled. Therefore the specimen is clamped, loaded with 5 test cycles and removed from the clamping device. Thereupon the strain gauges are set to zero and the specimen is clamped again, ready to be tested. The abort criteria are identical to those in the predecessor project P 1195 (10) and are chosen to correlate with a through-thickness cracking (N_3).

3.3 Previous test results

In this section the previous test results are presented. The fatigue strengths at 2×10^6 load cycles are evaluated using nominal stresses without consideration of strain gauge measurements, a fixed slope of $m = 5$ and a survival probability of $P = 50\%$. The tests were aborted after 5×10^6 load cycles and declared as run-out.

3.3.1 IPB-tests - Series A and B

The results of the so far carried out tests of series A and B are summarised in Fig. 6. For the load ratios $R = 0.5$ and $R = 0.1$ all cracks occurred at the weld toe on the tension side. For the tests with the load ratio $R = -1$, weld toe cracks and root cracks occurred on both sides. It is shown, that for $R = 0.1$ the fatigue strength of X-joints made from 1.4678 is 17% higher than that of joints made from

S460MH. The results show for both steel grades an increasing fatigue strength with decreasing load ratio (44% (series A) and 56% (series B) increase in fatigue strength for $R = 0.1$ compared to $R = 0.5$). This suggests a greater mean stress effect for the high-strength austenitic steel.

Fig. 6. Test results – a) Series A (results for $R = 0.1$ are taken from (10)), b) Series B (results for $R = 0.1/0.5$ are taken from (3))

3.3.2 AX-tests - Series C and G

The previous results of the series C and G are summarised in Fig. 7. For the load ratios $R = 0.5$ and $R = 0.1$ all cracks occurred at the weld toe. For the load ratio $R = “-\infty”$ the cracks occurred at the weld toe, as root cracks and diagonal to the weld seam, see Fig. 8. The results of series C (run-outs were not considered in the calculation of the regression) show a large increase (178%) in fatigue strength under compressive stresses. Compared to series A the axial tests result in a lower fatigue strength compared to the bending tests (25% reduction for $R = 0.1$). The results of Series G show an overall very low fatigue strength. Thus, the absolute difference between the load ratios is small. The relative differences between the fatigue strengths (41% increase in fatigue strength for $R = -1$ compared to $R = 0.5$) suggest the same tendency that is prevalent in the other test series.

Fig. 7. Test results – a) Series C, b) Series G (results for $R = 0.1$ are taken from (10))

Fig. 8. Fatigue cracks (series C) – a) weld toe crack ($R = 0.1$), b) diagonal crack ($R = "-\infty"$)

4 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

The previous test results suggest a not negligible mean stress effect for welded connections made of hollow sections that were not subjected to thermal stress relief. It could be shown that decreasing stress ratios correlate with increasing fatigue strength. In case of thin-walled hollow sections (Series A and B, $t = 2$ mm) the enhancement factor for the fatigue strength is even greater than the recommendation acc. (1) for components with low residual stresses, see Fig. 9. The fatigue tests under compressive stresses showed a very high increase in fatigue strength compared to the test under tensile stresses. Further fatigue tests will be carried out to quantify the influence of geometrical parameters and the material. In addition residual stress measurements will be performed. Based on these experimental tests a numerical parameter study will be conducted to develop a design recommendation for the nominal and notch stress concept to safely consider the mean stress effect. This is intended to enable an economical design of fatigue-loaded tubular joints to fully exploit the potential of mild and high-strength steels.

Fig. 9. Enhancement factors for the test series A, B and G

5 ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The research project FOSTA P 1603 “Berücksichtigung des Mittelspannungseinflusses bei Hohlprofilkonstruktionen aus niedrig- und hochfesten Stählen zur verbesserten Lebensdauerabschätzung” from the Research Association for steel Application (FOSTA) is supported by the German Federation of Industrial Research Associations (AiF) as part of the programme for promoting industrial cooperative research (IGF) based on a decision by the German Bundestag. The

project is carried out at University of Applied Sciences Munich. The authors would like to thank the project committee and the supporting companies for providing material and fabricating specimens.

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